

A Simple Hybrid Circuit Model for Folded Waveguide Structures

Thomas M. Antonsen¹, David Chernin¹, Alexander Vlasov, Igor Chernyavskiy, Khanh Nguyen², and Baruch Levush

Naval Research Laboratory
Washington, DC 20375

Abstract: A simple model for the dispersive properties of a folded waveguide slow wave structure is presented. The model, with a small number of fitting parameters, reproduces well the dispersion relation and Kino impedance of a structure as calculated using a computational electromagnetics code. The model allows for the inclusion of asymmetric beam tunnel fields and the stop bands introduced when the beam tunnel is misaligned.

Keywords: folded waveguide, dispersion relation, Kino impedance, misalignment, stop band.

Introduction

We analyze a simple model that can be used to simulate folded or serpentine waveguide circuits in both CHRISTINE [1] and TESLA [2]. The model that is considered is a mixture of a circuit model and a waveguide model similar to that of Booske et al. [3]. The mixture presents several advantages over pure circuit models [4,5], in that it gives a better fit to the dispersion relation of the structure over the frequency band of the two lowest modes of the structure. Because of this, the model will allow one to study competition between modes occurring at the intersections of the beam line with these two modes. Like the Curnow model [5], the parameters of this model are to be selected via fitting with properties of the fields determined by computational electromagnetic codes, that is, even though the model is based on a waveguide, it is not intended for the parameters of the model to be evaluated using the physical dimensions of the circuit of interest. Finally, the model provides a way to incorporate a description of asymmetric fields in the beam tunnel. This may be important to the beam wave interaction, particularly at the 2π point.

The basic unfolded model is illustrated in Fig. 1. The circuit is modeled as a transmission line with a cut-off frequency, ω_c that represents the basic folded waveguide. The line is periodically loaded by shunt admittances $Y_s(\omega)$ that model the effects of beam tunnels and bends in the waveguide. The shunt admittances are separated by an electrical distance L along the line, which supports waves with propagation constant, $\beta(\omega) = \sqrt{\omega^2 - \omega_c^2} / c$ and impedance, $Z_0 = Z_{00} / \sqrt{1 - \omega_c^2 / \omega^2}$. The shunt voltages, V_n , which also represent the beam tunnel voltages, alternate in polarity due to the folded nature of the waveguide.

Fig. 1. Unfolded transmission line and shunt admittances.

The dispersion relation for this structure can be obtained by representing the forward and backward propagating waves on each section of the transmission line in terms of the voltages at the shunts. The voltages are assumed to advance in phase from shunt to shunt according to $V_{n\pm 1} = V_n e^{\pm i\theta}$. Expressions for the currents $i_{\pm}(nL)$ entering the shunts are then obtained. Relating the current entering the shunt and the voltage across the shunt yields a dispersion relation,

$$\Delta \sin \beta L + \cos \beta L = -\cos \theta, \quad (1)$$

where $\Delta = Z_0 Y_s / (2i)$.

An example of a comparison of the dispersion relation (1) with one determined by a computational electromagnetics code (HFSS) for a G-band structure is shown in Fig.2. The dispersion curve was fit by matching the two cut-off frequencies at $\theta = 360^\circ$ and frequency in the center of the band $\theta = 270^\circ$ as indicated on the figure.

The shunt was modeled as a constant inductive reactance. The dispersion relation can also be fitted as well with a capacitive shunt. However, consideration of the Kino impedance shows an important distinction between capacitive and inductive shunts. The Kino impedance for the circuit is given by

$$Z_K = \frac{|V_n|^2}{2P} = -\frac{Z_0 \sin \beta L}{\sin \theta} \quad (2)$$

where P is the power flowing along the transmission line. The Kino impedance as a function of frequency is plotted in Fig. 3. With the choice of an inductive shunt the impedance goes to zero at the lower, $\theta = 360^\circ$ cut off frequency in accord with the impedance determined by HFSS. If the shunt is capacitive the impedance diverges at this frequency.

¹ SAIC, McLean, VA 22102

² Beam-Wave Research, Inc., Bethesda, MD 20814

Fig 2. Comparison of model and computational electromagnetics determined dispersion relations.

Fig. 3. Kino impedance for the model circuit and as determined by a computational electromagnetics code.

The value of the impedance of the transmission line, Z_{00} is adjusted to fit the impedance at the single frequency point indicated in Fig.3 and the resulting fit of the model [Eq.(2)] is seen to be excellent in this case.

The Kino impedance vanishes for the lower 2π mode for an inductive shunt. In the model this corresponds to the voltage on the line having a node at the location of each shunt. In a 3D structure this corresponds to the axial electric field vanishing at the axis of the beam. When this

occurs the field at the radius of the beam tunnel will vary roughly sinusoidally with the azimuthal angle ϕ . We can model this effect by defining an angle dependent voltage,

$$V_{gap}(\phi) = V_n [\cos(\beta r) + \Delta \sin(\beta r) - i \cos \phi \sin(\beta r) Z_0 / Z_k]. \quad (3)$$

where r is the radius of the beam tunnel. Thus, when the Kino impedance vanishes (and V_n vanishes too) the gap voltage is dominated by the $\cos \phi$ term; when the Kino impedance is large the constant term dominates.

Finally, we note that the model can be used to study the effect of misalignment (offset) of the beam tunnel. In this case we take the electrical lengths of the transmission line segments to alternate as $L \pm \delta L$. The structure is now periodic with twice the period. Thus, we look for solutions where $V_{n\pm 2} = V_n e^{\pm i\vartheta}$. We find

$$\cos^2\left(\frac{\vartheta}{2}\right) = \cos^2 \theta(\omega) - \Delta^2 \sin^2(\delta L \beta) \quad (4)$$

where $\cos \theta(\omega)$ is defined in Eq.(1). For small misalignment we obtain $\vartheta \approx 2\theta + 2m\pi$ as expected. However, stop bands appear near frequencies where $\cos \theta(\omega) \approx 0$ and the size of the stop band is proportional to the misalignment.

Acknowledgement

This work was supported by the Office of Naval Research.

References

1. Chernin, D., T. M. Antonsen, I. Chernyavskiy, A. Vlasov, B. Levush, R. Begum, and J. Legarra, "Large-Signal Multifrequency Simulation of Coupled Cavity TWTs", IEEE Trans. ED, 58, 1229-1240 (2011).
2. Vlasov, A.N., T.M. Antonsen, Jr., D. P. Chernin, B. Levush, and E.L. Wright, "Simulation of Microwave Devices with External Cavities Using MAGY," IEEE Trans. on Plasma Science, 30, 1277-1291 (2002).
3. Booske J.H, M. Converse, C Kory, C. Chevalier, D. Gallagher, K Kreischer, V Heinen, and S. Bhattacharjee, "Accurate Parametric Modeling of Folded Waveguide Circuits for Millimeter-Wave Travelling Wave Tubes," IEEE Trans. ED, 52, 685-694 (2005).
4. Sumathy, M., K.J. Vinoy, and S.K. Data, "Equivalent Circuit Analysis of Serpentine Folded-Waveguide Slow-wave Structures for Millimeter-wave Traveling-wave Tubes", J. Infrared Milli Terahz Waves 30, 151-158 (2009).
5. Curnow, H. "A general equivalent circuit for couple-cavity slow-wave structures", IEEE Trans MTT 13, 671-675 (1965).